

SURVEY: ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION OF CIVIL ENGINEERING STUDENTS

Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Male
Age Ranges	<input type="checkbox"/> 18 - 20 Years	<input type="checkbox"/> 20 - 25 Years
	<input type="checkbox"/> 25 - 30 Years	<input type="checkbox"/> More than 30 Years
Academic level	<input type="checkbox"/> Second year (BAC+2)	<input type="checkbox"/> License (BAC+3)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Master/ Engineer (BA+5)	<input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate (BAC+8)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineer School	<input type="checkbox"/> Faculty of Sciences
Establishment	<input type="checkbox"/> Faculty of Technical Sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> High Technical Certificate
	<input type="checkbox"/> Higher School of Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Institute Specialized of Applied Technology
	<input type="checkbox"/> Polytechnic School	
Field of studies	<input type="checkbox"/> Building	<input type="checkbox"/> Civil Engineering
	<input type="checkbox"/> Hydraulic and Environment	<input type="checkbox"/> Topography
Associative activity	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Entrepreneurship competition	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Name of Competition	<input type="checkbox"/> INJAZ Al-Maghib	<input type="checkbox"/> ISTA Entrepreneurial Innovation Program
	<input type="checkbox"/> Smart Bank by BMCE of AFRICA	<input type="checkbox"/> None
City	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Please rate your degree of agreement with the following statements using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 stands for "completely disagree" and 5 represents "completely agree."

			1	2	3	4	5
Entrepreneurial Attitude	Att1	If I have the opportunity and the resources, I will start a construction company					
	Att2	Among the different options, I prefer to be a contractor in construction					
	Att3	Being a contractor would bring me great satisfaction					
	Att4	A career as a construction contractor is attractive to me					
	Att5	Being a contractor means more benefits for me					
Entrepreneurial capacity	Cap1	Problem solving					
	Cap2	Creativity					
	Cap3	I can control the process of creating a new business in construction					
	Cap4	I know how to develop an entrepreneurial project					
	Cap5	Recognition of opportunities					
	Cap6	Networking and professional contacts					
	Cap7	I have knowledge of the practical details needed to start a construction company					
	Cap8	Starting and running a construction business would be easy for me					
	Cap9	Leadership and communication					
	Cap10	Writing a business plan?					
Entrepreneurial Intention	Int1	I will do everything I can to start and run my own construction business					
	Int2	I am determined to start a construction business in the future					
	Int3	My career goal is to become a construction contractor					
	Int4	I have seriously considered starting a construction business					
	Int5	I intend to start a construction business one day					
	Int6	I plan to start a construction business in the next 2-5 years					
Need for achievement	N4A1	I work too hard					
	N4A2	I work hard					
	N4A3	I am not very motivated to succeed					
	N4A4	I do just enough work to get by					
	N4A5	I work too little					
	N4A6	I am good at what I do					
Subjective Norms	SN1	Pedagogical Trainers					
	SN2	Friends					
	SN3	Family					